

Hysteresis and Reversibility in Calcium Ammonium Exchange in Bentonite

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The ion exchange equilibria involving calcium and ammonium in an Indian sample of bentonite were studied from several angles. The effect of time, pH, ionic strength and temperature on the exchanges has been investigated. Exchange of the counterions on the homoionic montmorillonite prepared by the salt saturation ion exchange method was nonstoichiometric, irreversible and gave rise to hysteresis loops in the exchange isotherms. Exchange at constant ionic strength gave rise to a reversal in the affinity order of the counterions over the clay surface. In both cases the hysteresis in the exchange isotherms appeared to be due to fixation and penetration of the ions into the clay micropores at high salt concentration. Attempts to restore reversibility were not successful. This system was, therefore, not amenable to a thermodynamic analysis as advocated by Gaines and Thomas and later workers.

SINCE plant nutrition and the physico-chemical properties of soils are largely controlled by the exchangeable cations on a clay surface, the replacement of cations is the most important of all soil phenomena. The classic experiments of Lemberg¹ clearly established the stoichiometry and reversibility of the process of ion exchange. Weigner² followed by others broadened this concept. The cation exchange in soils and clays was found to be affected by a number of factors such as fixation, blocking of sites by steric hindrance, lattice structure of clay minerals in relation to a particular cation, the nature and concentration of the reacting cation, pH and the time of interaction. In some cases the lyotropic series was followed and in others not.

Irreversibility of ion exchange processes in clays was quite frequently observed. Renold³ showed that in permutite, calcium ammonium and silver ammonium exchanges gave marked hysteresis. Wiegner⁴ in 1935 demonstrated that for calcium ammonium exchange, effect of order of entry was greatest in permutite and least in bentonite. Vanselow⁵ demonstrated that calcium-barium and barium-copper exchanges gave no hysteresis nor did magnesium-calcium exchange. Faucher and Thomas⁶ demonstrated perfect reversibility during adsorption studies on clay minerals. It was shown by Tabikh, Barshad and Overstreet⁷ that treatments of the clay that enhanced its aggregation led to an increase of the apparent irreversibility and that reversibility could be restored upon recycling a clay in a hydrogen resin column. More recently, Van Bladel and Laudelout⁸ described hysteresis effects as a consequence of the

imperfection of dispersion of flocculated clays, e.g., by divalent cations and the ensuing inaccessibility of some exchange sites. The extent of irreversible adsorption of cobalt and zinc ions in sodium montmorillonite was shown by Maes and Cremers⁹ to depend upon the composition of the solid phase and pH, and that the reaction could be made reversible by a pH decrease.

In view of its importance cation exchange equilibria has been extensively studied and a number of equations^{5, 10, 11} have been proposed to quantitatively characterize the phenomenon. The subject was given a thermodynamic treatment by Gaines and Thomas^{1, 2} as well as by other workers^{1, 3}. These treatments were, however, based on a complete reversibility of exchange which may not always be present. The present study was, therefore, designed to investigate the ion exchange involving calcium and ammonium on 'Akli' bentonite and to study the reversibility of the reaction under differing conditions so as to examine the possibility of a quantitative expression for the exchange with the help of thermodynamic analysis.

Materials and Methods

The bentonite used in these studies was obtained from the Director, Geological Survey of India, Rajasthan. X-ray studies showed that the fine fraction ($< 2\mu$) of the sample from "Akli" obtained after removal of organic matter and saturation with 2N NaCl followed by centrifugation consisted mainly of montmorillonite.

Sodium bentonite was prepared by the method of Aldrich and Buchanan¹⁴ in which the clay suspension was saturated with 1*N* NaCl and washed with deionised water till free from chloride ions and till the conductivity became very low and constant. The calcium bentonite and ammonium bentonite suspensions were then prepared from the sodium bentonite suspension by saturating it with 1*N* CaCl₂ in case of the calcium clay and 1*N* NH₄Cl in case of the ammonium clay, respectively, and then washing to remove the excess salts. The concentration of the suspensions as determined by evaporation was 15.1 and 15.2 g per litre respectively.

The CEC values of the calcium bentonite and ammonium bentonite were determined by extraction of the calcium and ammonium saturated suspensions with a solution of 0.1*N* HCl in 1*N* NaCl and then respectively estimating calcium and ammonium ions¹⁵ released. The values obtained were 67.4 and 80.3 meq/100 g respectively.

Since equilibrium distribution of exchangeable cations is of utmost importance in ion exchange studies, investigations were first made to determine the length of time required for the completion of the interaction between the exchangeable cations on bentonite. For the study of calcium exchange on ammonium clay, three sets of 10 ml suspensions of ammonium clay were treated with 1, 10 and 15 ml of .04*N* CaCl₂ and 14, 5 and 0 ml of .06*N* NH₄Cl solutions respectively, the latter addition having been made to attain a total ionic strength equal to 0.036. The mixtures were shaken for one hour at room

hours. After the requisite interval of time, mixtures were centrifuged and the calcium in the supernatants was estimated by titration with a standard solution of EDTA. The amount of calcium adsorbed at different intervals of time was then obtained from the amount of calcium added minus the calcium remaining in the supernatants. A similar procedure was followed for determining the effect of time on ammonium exchange on calcium clay; ammonium having been estimated spectrophotometrically with Nessler's reagent at 400μ. The results are represented (vide Fig. 1, 2.)

Since the nature of cation exchange is controlled to a considerable extent by pH, an investigation was made of the effect of pH on calcium ammonium exchange on the bentonite surface. For this purpose ammonium and calcium bentonite suspensions were treated with 0.1*N* HNO₃ and 0.1*N* NH₄OH to obtain the desired levels of pH. Exchange was then carried out at constant ionic strength in the forward and reverse direction, respectively as described above, to equilibrium point by shaking the mixture for 3 hours. The results are represented in Fig. 2, curves.

The exchange isotherms were determined for both ammonium and calcium bentonite in forward and reverse directions with and without adjustment of total ionic strength at a pH value of 4.5 at two different temperatures.

For the exchange experiments two separate sets of 10 ml. samples of ammonium and calcium bentonite suspensions after the adjustment of pH to 4.5

Fig 1. Effect of time on exchange. Closed circles (●) indicate Ca exchange on NH₄-bentonite and open circles (○) NH₄ exchange on Ca-bentonite.

temperature. Similar exchanges were carried out at 2, 3, 6, 9, and 12 hours also along with a blank at 0

Fig 2. Effect of pH on the exchange, Closed circles (●) indicate Ca exchange on NH₄-bentonite and open circles (○) NH₄ exchange on Ca-bentonite.

with dil. HNO₃ were taken in a large number of glass stoppered tubes. In one set of experiments the ionic

strength of the samples was adjusted to a constant value as described in the case of time effect and in the other case the suspensions were taken as such. The suspensions were then treated with different amounts of $0.04N$ $CaCl_2$ in case of ammonium bentonite and $.06N$ NH_4Cl in case of calcium bentonite along with deionised water if any to provide a constant volume of 25 ml. The mixtures were shaken for 3 hours to attain equilibrium at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ both in the forward and backward direction in a thermostatic water bath. The same procedure was repeated in the batches involving the next higher temperature viz., $60 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The suspensions were then centrifuged and ammonium and calcium estimated in the supernatants as per the usual methods. The corresponding concentrations of ammonium or calcium in the solid bentonite phase were obtained by subtraction of the ammonium or calcium concentration in the supernatants from the ammonium or calcium bentonite CEC. Similarly the amount of the cation concerned (Ca^{2+} or NH_4^+) taken up by the bentonite surface in replacing the corresponding cation was obtained by difference between the amount of cation added and the amount of cation remaining in equilibrium suspension.

Results and Discussion

The results of calcium ammonium exchange on bentonite as affected by time, pH, ionic strength and temperature are presented in the following paragraphs.

An examination of Fig. 1 indicated a slow increase in exchange in case of both the exchanging cations with increase in length of time till the system attained equilibrium at 3 hours in each case both in the forward as well as reverse direction. This period, therefore, appeared to be suitable for carrying out further experiments on these exchanges.

An examination of the data (vide Fig. 2) showed that at all the three concentrations of the exchanging cation added, the pH had a significant influence on the extent of cation exchanged. The exchange increased with pH till it reached a maximum value at pH 6 and thereafter declined. In the case of highest range of concentration studied the calcium exchanged on ammonium clay was in the neighbourhood of CEC of ammonium clay at a pH value of 4.5 and in excess of CEC over it. In the case of reverse exchange the amount of ammonium exchanged was in the neighbourhood of CEC of calcium clay at pH 4.5 and in excess of CEC over the value of pH. The observations were in agreement with that of Bower and Truog¹⁶ who showed that certain ions like Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} and Fe^{2+} were retained by montmorillonite in quantities greater than the exchange capacity. They concluded that hydroxy ions were in competition with the normal ions for exchange sites on bentonite at higher pH. To avoid such effect the exchanges were, therefore, carried out at pH value of 4.5.

For a plot of the exchange isotherms the concen-

Fig. 3. Exchange isotherms of calcium ammonium exchange on bentonite at 30 and $60^\circ C$ without adjustment of ionic strength of exchanging solutions.

tration of the ions concerned (NH_4^+ or Ca^{2+}) in the bentonite phases and in the solutions were calculated in terms of equivalent ionic fractions¹⁷. The values obtained at 30 and 60° for the exchanges both in the forward and reverse directions without and with adjustment of total ionic strength are represented in Figs. 3 and 4, respectively.

An examination of the curves for calcium exchange with ammonium bentonite (Fig. 3, curves 1, 2) and of ammonium exchange with calcium bentonite (Fig. 3, curves 3, 4) showed that the isotherms deviated to different sides of the diagonal when the exchanges

ionic strength of the exchanging solutions (Fig. 4, curves 1 to 4). The adjustment of ionic strength to a constant value involved addition of a common cation which increased X_{NH_4} or X_{Ca} (equivalent

ionic fraction of the ammonium or calcium ion respectively in solution) resulting in an increase in the values of selectivity quotient¹⁷,

$$K_C = \frac{\bar{X}_{\text{Ca}}}{(\bar{X}_{\text{NH}_4})^2} \frac{(X_{\text{NH}_4})^2}{\bar{X}_{\text{Ca}}} \quad \text{for the calcium}$$

Fig. 4. Exchange isotherms of calcium ammonium exchange on bentonite at 30 and 60°C at constant ionic strength of exchanging solutions.

were carried out in the forward and backward directions without adjustment of ionic strength. At both the temperatures calcium did replace ammonium ions in the case of calcium exchange with ammonium bentonite but the preference of the bentonite was lower for calcium than for ammonium (Fig. 3, curves 1, 2). On the other hand, in case of ammonium exchange with calcium bentonite, the preference of the clay was greater for calcium than for ammonium (Fig. 3, curves 3, 4). The preferences also differed with temperature being higher at 60° in both cases.

A reversal took place in the order of preferences by bentonite for calcium or ammonium when the exchanges were carried out at a fixed value of total

exchange on ammonium bentonite. This resulted in the observed reversal in the affinity order of the counterions over the clay surface. Changes in the hydration of ions and electrostatic interactions on addition of the electrolyte appeared to be responsible for this interesting behaviour.

These observations indicated that in exchanges where total ionic strength was not made constant the bentonite preferred a cation originally present on its surface in comparison to the cation being added later. On the other hand, at constant ionic strength the bentonite preferred the exchanging cation in comparison to one originally present on its surface. The exchanges were thus different when approached from different sides and at different ionic strengths.

Such effects in ion exchange equilibria have been reported by earlier workers and also in these laboratories in exchanges involving Na^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} and Zn^{2+} ions on bentonites and illites¹⁸.

The differences in equilibria, therefore, resulted in formation of hysteresis loops during these investigations (Figs. 3 and 4). The main cause for the occurrence of hysteresis loops appeared to be the fixation or penetration of ammonium or calcium ions into the micropores or cavities of ammonium or calcium clays due to the long saturation of the bentonite by the corresponding salt during the preparation of the homoionic clay by the salt saturation method of Aldrich and Buchanan⁴. Hysteresis has also been reported by Maes and Cremers⁹ in case of adsorption of cobalt and zinc ions in sodium montmorillonite at very high occupancy approaching saturation of divalent cations.

Here we had, therefore, systems in which, in one case at high ion occupancy a part of ammonium was fixed and not replaceable whereas in the other case a part of calcium was fixed and not exchangeable. Van Bladel and Laudelout⁸ who also observed a like phenomenon described such apparent irreversibility due to changes in aggregation of clay particles by divalent cations causing inaccessibility of some exchange sites.

Further experiments in these laboratories to examine if reversibility could be restored by carrying out exchange experiments with freshly prepared clays at low and intermediate ion occupancy did not prove successful and hysteresis of exchange still persisted. Under no circumstances explored, herein, the calcium ammonium exchange, therefore, appeared

truly reversible and amenable to thermodynamic analysis based upon Gaines and Thomas model^{1,2}.

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